

FLEXURAL-TORSION VIBRATION CONTROL OF FIBER COMPOSITE CANTILEVERED BEAM BY USING PIEZO-ACTUATORS

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ABSTRACT

In the experiment two piezoceramic actuators are prepared. One is adhered to the beam along the structural axis, where it is called ACT1. Another is attached perpendicular to the principal axis of elasticity (abbreviated to PAE) of the beam, where it is called ACT2. The direction of PAE is found, and natural frequencies of flexural and torsional vibration are obtained by the experiment. Vibration behavior of the beam is examined by the forced vibration tests when ACT1 and/or ACT2 are operated, and the experimental result is tried to be substantiated by simulation using the equations of motion.

INTRODUCTION

Flexural-torsion vibration takes place in mechanical structures under dynamic loadings if the center of gravity of a fiber composite beam is off the principal axis of elasticity. In such cases, the flexural vibration can be restrained comparatively easily by using suitable vibration suppression devices, but the torsional vibration cannot be controlled so easily. There are several studies on flexural and torsional control of composite beams and plates[1],[2].

In this study, flexural-torsion vibration control is investigated for fiber composite cantilevered beam having an eccentric mass. The direction of PAE is found based on the definition of PAE in the static tests, and natural frequencies of flexural and torsional mode are obtained by spectrum analysis in the vibration tests. In the forced vibration tests under sinusoidal excitation having natural frequency of flexural or torsional vibration, the effect of the negative velocity relayed feedback of deflection and/or angle of torsion of the beam through ACT1 and/or ACT2 on the vibration behavior of the beam is examined. For substantiation of the forced vibration tests, simulation using the equations of motion with two degree-of-freedom and the control theory is conducted.

SPECIMEN AND EXPERIMENT

SPECIMEN

The specimen used in experiment is a cantilevered composite beam which is produced by eight layers of symmetric laminated plates formed out of GFRP prepreg, and the stacking sequence of the beam is $[30^\circ/-30^\circ]_{2s}$. Two piezoceramic actuators and three strain gauges are attached to the beam. That is, one is adhered along the structural axis of the beam at the neighborhood of the fixed end of the beam for flexural vibration control, where it is called ACT1. Another is also adhered at an angle of 45° to the specimen at a distance of 60 mm from the fixed end of the beam for torsional vibration control, where it is called ACT2. An arm made of aluminum for equipping an eccentric mass is attached to the beam at the free end as shown in Fig.1. In this figure m_s , m_a , L_a , L , B , S and L_e are the eccentric mass, the mass and the length of an arm, the length and the width of a beam, the distance between the free end of the beam and the eccentric mass, and the distance between the center of the free end of the beam and the intersection of the arm and PAE.

Figure 1. Geometry of specimen including two piezo-actuators and an eccentric mass.

MEASUREMENT OF PAE AND NATURAL FREQUENCIES

In the static flexural and torsional vibration test, load and torque was applied to the arm with an eccentric mass, and the displacements y_L and y_R of the both ends of the arm were measured varying the distance S between the free end of the beam and the eccentric mass. The deflection δ_L and the angle of torsion θ_L at the free end of the beam can be obtained from y_R and y_L . PAE is a symmetric axis with respect to elastic distortion and a load on the axis does not yield any torsion, therefore the direction of PAE can be found when the angle of torsion θ_L is zero.

Next, the natural frequencies are derived by spectrum analysis of response wave of the displacements of the both ends of the arm in the case of randomly vibrating the fixed end of the beam. It is confirmed that the experimental results of PAE and natural frequencies agree well with the theoretical results which are obtained by solving the characteristic equation for a simplified vibration equation of two degree-of-freedom system(See Table 1).

Table 1.Theoretical and experimental results for PAE and natural frequencies for two mode.

	Theo.	Exp.
Principal axis of elasticity L_e (mm)	26.3	26.2
Natural frequency for the 1st flexural mode (Hz)	10.0	9.0
Natural frequency for the 1st torsional mode (Hz)	37.5	36.0

FORCED VIBRATION TESTS

The displacement of the upper end and that of the lower end of the arm attached to the beam was measured by two non-contacting laser displacement pickups, and the information was fed to a personal computer through an A/D converter. The deflection was obtained by the average of the displacements of the upper and lower ends, and the angle of torsion was obtained by the difference between them. The amount of the feedback voltage was calculated by a personal computer based on the velocity feedback through a relay element, and the voltage signal was applied to the attached piezoceramics through a D/A converter. That is, the negative feedback voltage which is switched by the signal of the deflection velocity through relay element was applied to ACT1. In the same manner, the negative feedback voltage switched by the signal of the angle velocity of torsion was applied to ACT2.

The fixed end of the beam is vibrated forcedly under the sinusoidal excitation having natural frequency of the 1st flexural or torsional mode using the vibration testing facility, and vibration behavior of the beam is examined when the two piezoceramic actuators are operated.

First, the vibration tests were conducted when an eccentric mass was placed at the distance of 40 mm from the center of the free end of the beam. That is, $S=40$. Fig.2 shows frequency spectra of the displacement of the lower end of the arm under sinusoidal excitation having natural frequency of the 1st flexural mode. The case in which no piezoceramic actuator was operated is shown in Fig.2(a). The vibration of flexural mode is diminished, but the vibration of torsional mode appears remarkably as shown in Fig.2(b) when only ACT1 was operated. It can be considered that the supply of energy due to the forced excitation moves to the torsional mode coupled with the flexural mode as the vibration of flexural mode is suppressed by operating ACT1. The vibration of both flexural mode and torsional modes was greatly diminished as shown in Fig.2(c) when ACT2 in addition to ACT1 was also operated at the same time. Fig.3 shows frequency spectra of the beam under sinusoidal excitation having natural frequency of the 1st torsional mode. The case in which no piezoceramic actuator was

operated is shown in Fig.3(a). The vibration of torsional mode is diminished, but the vibration of flexural mode appears remarkably as shown in Fig.3(b) when only ACT2 was operated. Moreover peaks due to the composition of the 1st flexural and the 1st torsional modes as will be seen in nonlinear vibration appear, for example, in the neighborhood of 27 Hz. The vibration of both flexural and torsional modes is greatly diminished as shown in Fig.3(c) when both ACT1 and ACT2 were operated simultaneously, but the vibration of torsional mode was not completely suppressed because of the shortage of powers supplied by piezoceramic actuators.

Next, the vibration tests were conducted when an eccentric mass was placed on the PAE in

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 2. Frequency spectra of a cantilivered composite beam under sinusoidal excitation having natural frequency 9 Hz of the 1st flexural mode for $S=40(\text{mm})$.

- (a) ACT1 Off and ACT2 Off,
- (b) ACT1 On and ACT2 Off,
- (c) ACT1 On and ACT2 On.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 3. Frequency spectra of a cantilivered composite beam under sinusoidal excitation having natural frequency 36 Hz of the 1st torsional mode for $S=40(\text{mm})$.

- (a) ACT1 Off and ACT2 Off,
- (b) ACT1 Off and ACT2 On,
- (c) ACT1 On and ACT2 On.

much the same way as the case of $S=40$. In this case, the similar results to the case of $S=40$ were obtained, but the torsional vibration was more suppressed than that for the case of $S=40$.

ANALYSIS BY SIMULATION

STATE EQUATION OF VIBRATION SYSTEM

A fiber composite cantilevered beam having an eccentric mass is considered to be two degree-of-freedom system concerning the deflection δ_L and the angle of torsion θ_L of the free end of the beam.

When load and torque are applied at the free end of the beam, the following equations are obtained based on the equilibrium of force and moment and the laminated plate theory[3].

$$\ddot{\delta}_L + \mu_1 \dot{\theta}_L + \omega_1^2 \delta_L + \omega_2^2 \theta_L = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\ddot{\theta}_L + \frac{1}{\mu_2} \dot{\theta}_L + \frac{\omega_1^2}{\mu_1} \delta_L + \frac{\omega_2^2}{\mu_2} \theta_L = 0 \quad (2)$$

where $\mu_1, \mu_2, \omega_1, \omega_2$ are coefficients calculated from m_a, m_s, S , the stiffness matrix and geometrical parameters of a fiber composite beam.

It is considered that the lumped load $p(t)$ is applied on the center of the free end of the beam when an input voltage is applied to ACT1 and the torque $q(t)$ is applied on the center of the free end of the beam when an input voltage is applied to ACT2. In this case, the motion equation of the vibration system can be expressed by the following equations regarding the lumped load or the torque as the external force $u(t)$ applied to the system.

$$\ddot{\delta}_L + \mu_1 \dot{\theta}_L + \omega_1^2 \delta_L + \omega_2^2 \theta_L = au \quad (3)$$

$$\ddot{\theta}_L + \frac{1}{\mu_2} \dot{\theta}_L + \frac{\omega_1^2}{\mu_1} \delta_L + \frac{\omega_2^2}{\mu_2} \theta_L = bu, \quad (4)$$

where $a = \frac{1}{m_a + m_s}$, $b=0$ when only ACT1 is operated, and $a=0$, $b = \frac{1}{m_s S}$ when only ACT2 is operated.

The system given by Eqns (3) and (4) can be expressed by state equations as shown in Eqn (5).

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{B}u \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}, \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4)^T = (\delta_L, \dot{\delta}_L, \theta_L, \dot{\theta}_L)^T$, $\mathbf{y} = (\delta_L, \theta_L)^T$, \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{C} are coefficient matrices and vectors.

The transfer function $G_b(s)$ of fiber composite beam is derived as Eqn (7).

$$G_b(s) = C(sI - A)^{-1}B = \begin{pmatrix} G_{b1}(s) \\ G_{b2}(s) \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

TRANSFER CHARACTERISTICS OF PIEZO-ACTUATORS

The transfer function of the beam including piezo-actuator was obtained by experiment in order to obtain the relation between the voltage applied to the piezo-actuators and the deflection or the angle of torsion at the free end of the beam. The bode diagram $G_{II}(s)$ of the transfer function from the voltage applied to ACT1 to the deflection can be derived by the experiment.

On the other hand, the transfer function $G_{b1}(s)$ of the beam from the output of ACT1 to the deflection of the beam can be calculated by Eqn (7). The transfer functions of ACT1 and ACT2 were supposed to be expressed by the following equations.

$$G_{p1}(s) = K_{m1} K_1 (1 + T_{p1}s), \quad (8)$$

$$G_{p2}(s) = K_{m2} K_2 (1 + T_{p2}s), \quad (9)$$

where K_1 and K_2 are proportional constants determined by the voltage applied to ACT1 or ACT2 and the strain of the beam. Each value of parameters K_{m1} and T_{p1} in Eqn (8) was determined as follows. Since the break frequency of $G_{p1}(s)$ can be considered to be the natural frequency ω_1 of the beam, the value of T_{p1} was determined to be 1.77×10^{-2} . The value of K_{m1} was determined to be 1.20×10^2 by overlapping of the transfer function $G_{b1}(s)$ and $G_{II}(s)$. The value of K_{m2} and T_{p2} could be determined in the same way as K_{m1} and T_{p1} .

CONTROL OF FORCED VIBRATION BASED ON VELOCITY RELAYED FEEDBACK

The case of vibrating the fixed end of the beam forcedly under sinusoidal excitation f having natural frequency ω_1 of the 1st flexural mode using velocity feedback of deflection through a relay element as controller when only ACT1 is operated was simulated, where $S=40$. The block diagram of the equivalent system in this case is shown in Fig.4.

Figure 4. Block diagram of the system equivalent to the control system of forced vibration.

Figure 5. Response of deflection δ_L and angle of torsion θ_L under sinusoidal excitation having natural frequency of the 1st flexural mode for $S=40$ (mm)

- (a) ACT1 Off and ACT2 Off,
- (b) ACT1 On and ACT2 Off.

In this case, $f(t)$ and $f'(t)$ are shown as Eqns (10) and (11), respectively.

$$f(t) = P_1 \sin \omega_1 t, \quad (10)$$

$$f'(t) = L^{-1} \left[\frac{F(s)}{G_{p1}(s)} \right], \quad (11)$$

where $F(s) = L[f(t)]$. In Fig.4, $G_1(s)$ represents the transfer function produced by combination of $G_{p1}(s)$ and $G_b(s)$. The system given by the transfer function $G_1(s)$ can be also expressed by state equations.

The simulation result based on the discrete-time state equations[4] derived from the above mentioned state equations is shown in Fig.5. This figure shows that the flexural vibration is diminished, but the torsional vibration is amplified when only ACT1 is operated.

CONCLUSIONS

Control effect of flexural-torsion coupling vibration of fiber composite cantilevered beam by using two piezo-actuators is examined by the experiment of forced vibration of the beam. As a result, it is found that the effect of negative relayed velocity feedback of deflection or angle of torsion through each piezo-actuator has different influence on the control of the two vibration modes respectively. By simulation using control theory and motion equations with two degree-of-freedom derived based on the laminated plate theory and the equilibrium of forces and moments, the particular phenomenon appeared in the experiment can be explained.

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